

DECOMPOSITION OF GRAPHS INTO INTERNALLY DISJOINT TREES

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Abstract: A Smarandache graphoidal tree (k, d) -cover of a graph G is a partition of edges of G into trees T_1, T_2, \dots, T_l such that $|E(T_i) \cap E(T_j)| \leq k$ and $|T_i| \leq d$ for integers $1 \leq i, j \leq l$. In this paper we investigate the graphoidal tree covering number $\gamma_T(G)$, i.e., Smarandache graphoidal tree $(0, \infty)$ -cover of complete graphs, complete bipartite graphs and products of paths and cycles. In [5] M.F.Foregger, define a parameter $z'(G)$ as the minimum number of subsets into which the vertex set of G can be partitioned so that each subset induces a tree. In this paper we also establish the relation $z'(G) \leq \gamma_T(G)$.

Key Words: Smarandache graphoidal tree (k, d) -cover, graphoidal tree cover, complete graph, complete bipartite graph, product of path and cycle.

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§1. Introduction

By a graph we mean a finite, undirected graphs without loops and multiple edges. Terms not defined here are used in the sense of Harary [6]. Any vertex of a graph H of degree greater than 1 is called an internal vertex of H . A *Smarandache graphoidal tree (k, d) -cover* of a graph G is a partition of edges of G into trees T_1, T_2, \dots, T_l such that $|E(T_i) \cap E(T_j)| \leq k$ and $|T_i| \leq d$ for integers $1 \leq i, j \leq l$. Particularly, a Smarandache graphoidal tree $(0, \infty)$ -cover, usually called a *graphoidal tree cover* of G is a collection of non C trivial trees in G such that

- (i) every vertex is an internal vertex of at most one tree;
- (ii) every edge is in exactly one tree.

Let \mathcal{G} denote the set of all graphoidal tree covers of G . Since $E(G)$ is a graphoidal tree cover, we have $\mathcal{G} \neq \emptyset$. We define the graphoidal tree covering number of a graph G to be the minimum number of trees in anygraphoidal tree cover of G , and denote it by $\gamma_T(G)$. Any

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graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{T} of G for which $|\mathcal{T}| = \gamma_T(G)$ is called a minimum graphoidal tree cover.

Example 1.1 Consider a graph G given in the Fig.1.

Fig.1

Let T_1, T_2 and T_3 be the trees in Fig.2.

Fig.2

It is easy to see that the graph G in Fig.1 cannot be covered by two trees. Since the three trees shown in Fig.2 form a graphoidal tree cover, $\gamma_T(G) = 3$.

Observation 1.2 If $\deg(v) > \gamma_T(G)$, then v is an internal vertex in some tree in every minimum graphoidal tree cover.

Observation 1.3 For a (p, q) graph G , $\gamma_T(G) \geq \lceil \frac{q}{p-1} \rceil$.

Observation 1.4 $\gamma_T(G) > \frac{\delta(G)}{2}$ if $\delta(G) > 0$.

§2. Preliminaries

$\tau(G)$ is the minimum number of subsets into which the edge set $E(G)$ of G can be partitioned so that each subset forms a tree. A cyclically 4-edge connected graph is one in which the removal of no three edges will disconnect the graph into two components such that each component

contains a cycle. We state some preliminary results from [2] and [4].

Theorem 2.1([4]) $\tau(K_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$.

Theorem 2.2([2]) *If G is a 2-connected cubic graph with p vertices, $p \geq 8$, then $\tau(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{p}{4} \rfloor$.*

Theorem 2.3([2]) *If G is a 3-connected cubic graph with p vertices, $p \geq 12$, then $\tau(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{p}{6} \rfloor$.*

Theorem 2.4([2]) *If G is a cyclically 4-edge connected cubic graph with p vertices, $8 \leq p \leq 16$ then $\tau(G) = 2$.*

§3. Complete and complete bipartite graphs

We first determine the graphoidal tree covering number of a complete graphs.

Theorem 3.1 $\gamma_T(K_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$.

Proof From observation 1.4, it follows that $\gamma_T(K_n) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$. We give a construction for the reverse inclusion. First, let n be even, say $n = 2k$. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, let T_i be the tree shown in Fig.3 (subscripts modulo n). The Standard Rotation Method shows that this is true. (see Fig.4 for the case $n = 8$).

Fig.3

Fig.4

For n odd, delete one vertex from each tree in the decomposition given for K_{n+1} . The result is clearly a graphoidal tree cover for K_n , once isolated vertices are removed. \square

We now turn to the case of complete bipartite graphs, beginning with a general result on the diameter of trees in a minimum graphoidal tree cover. The following standard notation is used for the partite sets of $K_{m,n}$ with $m \leq n$: $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$.

Lemma 3.2 *If a minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J} of $K_{m,n}$ contains a tree with a path of length ≥ 5 , then it also contains a tree with exactly one edge.*

Proof Let $T \in \mathcal{J}$ contain a path $P = (x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3, \dots)$ where $x_i \in X$ and $y_j \in Y$. Since y_1 and x_3 are internal in T , these cannot be internal in any other member of \mathcal{J} . Therefore $T_1 = \{(y_1 x_3)\} \in \mathcal{J}$. \square

Lemma 3.3 *If $m \leq n \leq 2mC - 3$, $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \geq \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$.*

Proof Suppose $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) = r$ with $r < \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$. Let \mathcal{J} be a minimum graphoidal tree cover of $K_{m,n}$. Since $\delta(G) = m > \frac{m+n}{3} > r$ (as $n \leq 2mC - 3$), by Observation 1.3, we have every vertex is an internal vertex of a tree in \mathcal{J} .

Claim 1. No tree in \mathcal{J} can have more than two internal vertices from X with a common neighbor from Y . Suppose x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k ($k \geq 3$) are all adjacent to y_1 in T_1 of \mathcal{J} . Then the sum of degrees of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k in T_1 is at most $n + k - 1$. But each x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) is an end vertex in at most $r - 1$ other members of \mathcal{J} . So they have at most $n + k - 1 + k(r - 1)$ total adjacencies in \mathcal{J} . Since $r < \frac{m+n}{3}$, $n + k - 1 + k(r - 1) < \frac{3n + 3k - 3 + k(m+n) - 3k}{3} \leq \frac{n(2k+3)}{3} - 1$ ($m \leq n$) $= nk - (\frac{n(k-3)}{3} + 1) < nk$ ($k \geq 3$), a contradiction. Hence we have Claim 1.

Claim 2 There exists a minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}' such that no tree in \mathcal{J}' has a path of length ≥ 5 .

Suppose $T_1 \in \mathcal{J}$ has a path $(x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3, \dots)$. Then by the previous lemma, a tree T_2 in \mathcal{J} has just the single edge $y_1 x_3$. Let T'_1 be the tree containing x_2 obtained by removing the edge $y_1 x_2$ from T_1 . Let T'_2 be the tree $(T_1 - T'_1) \cup T_2$. Let \mathcal{J}'_1 be the graphoidal tree cover obtained from \mathcal{J} after replacing T_1, T_2 by T'_1, T'_2 respectively. If there is a tree in \mathcal{J}'_1 again contains a path of length ≥ 5 we repeat this process for \mathcal{J}'_1 and so on. Finally we get the required minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}' . Hence we get Claim 2.

Now we can assume that no tree in \mathcal{J} has a path of length ≥ 5 .

Claim 3 No tree in \mathcal{J} can have more than two internal vertices from Y with a common neighbor from X .

Suppose there is a tree T_1 in \mathcal{J} containing k internal vertices y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k ($k \geq 3$) with a common neighbor x_1 . Since $m > \gamma_T(G)$ and every vertex is an internal vertex of a tree in \mathcal{J} , there is a tree in \mathcal{J} , say, T_2 containing at least two vertices from X as internal vertices. By Claim 2, the internal vertices of a tree in \mathcal{J} form a star and so the internal vertices from X in T_2 have a common neighbor from Y . By Claim 1, T_2 has exactly two internal vertices x_2 and x_3 from X with a common neighbor y_s from Y . Between x_2, x_3 and y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k there are $2k$ edges in $K_{m,n}$. Clearly x_2 and x_3 can be made adjacent with two y 's in T_1 . Let

it be y_1 and y_2 . Now y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k can be made adjacent with x 's in T_2 . But it will cover exactly $k + 2$ edges (out of $2k$ edges) and so by the definition of graphoidal tree cover, each uncovered edge is a tree in \mathcal{J} . Without loss of generality let T_3, T_4, \dots, T_k be the trees with edges $(y_3, x_{l_3}), (y_4, x_{l_4}), \dots, (y_k, x_{l_k})$ respectively, where $l_i \in \{2, 3\}$, $3 \leq i \leq k$. By Claim 2 the internal vertices of T_1 form a star. Removing all the edges incident with y_i from T_1 to form the tree T'_i ($3 \leq i \leq k$). Let T'_1 be the tree formed by the remaining edges of T_1 after the removal. Now each T_i in \mathcal{J} is replaced by $T'_i \cup T_i$ for $3 \leq i \leq k$. Also replace T_1 in \mathcal{J} by T'_1 . If \mathcal{J} again contains a tree having more than two internal vertices from Y with a common neighbor from X . We repeat the above process and so on. Hence we have Claim 3. From Claims 1, 2 and 3, it follows that no tree in \mathcal{J} has more than three internal vertices. Since every vertex of $K_{m,n}$ must be an internal vertex of a tree in \mathcal{J} and $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) = r$, we have only $3r$ ($< m + n$) internal vertices in \mathcal{J} . This is a contradiction. Hence $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \geq \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$. \square

Theorem 3.4 *If $m \leq n \leq 2m - 3$, then $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) = \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$. Furthermore, if $n > 2m - 3$, then $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) = m$.*

Proof By Lemma 3.3, $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \geq \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$. Next we proceed to prove $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \leq \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$, where $3 \leq m \leq n \leq 2m - 3$. Let $r = \lfloor \frac{2mn}{3} \rfloor = \frac{2m-n+k}{3}$ where k is 0, 1 or 2.

Define for $1 \leq i \leq r$

$$P_i = \{(x_i, y_i x_{r+i})\} \cup \{(y_i, x_j) : j \neq i, r+i; 1 \leq j \leq m-k\} \cup \{(x_i, y_j) : r < j \leq m-r-k\} \cup \{(x_{r+i}, y_j) : m-r-k < j \leq n-k\}.$$

For $1 \leq i \leq m-2r-k$ we define

$$P_{i+r} = \{(y_{r+i}, x_{2r+i}, y_{m-r-k+i})\} \cup \{(x_{2r+i}, y_j); j \neq r+i, m-r-k+i, r < j \leq n-k\} \cup \{(y_{r+i}, x_j) : r+1 \leq j \leq 2r\} \cup \{(y_{m-r-k+i}, x_j) : 1 \leq j \leq r\}.$$

For $k = 1$

$$P_{m-r} = \{(x_m, y_n)\} \cup \{(x_m, y_j) : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\} \cup \{(y_n, x_j) : 1 \leq j \leq m-1\}.$$

For $k = 2$

$$P_{m-r-1} = \{(x_{m-1}, y_{n-1})\} \cup \{(x_{m-1}, y_j) : 1 \leq j \leq n-2\} \cup \{(y_{n-1}, x_j) : 1 \leq j \leq m-2\},$$

$$P_{m-r} = \{(x_m, y_n)\} \cup \{(x_m, y_j) : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\} \cup \{(y_n, x_j) : 1 \leq j \leq m-1\}.$$

Clearly $\mathcal{J} = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{m-r}\}$ is a graphoidal tree cover for $K_{m,n}$. Therefore $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \leq m-r = \frac{m+n+k}{3} \leq \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$.

Let $n = 2m - 2 + k$, $k \geq 0$. Suppose that $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \neq m$. Then there exists a graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J} with at most $m - 1$ trees. Since $\delta(G) > m - 1$, it follows that every vertex is an internal vertex of a tree in \mathcal{J} . If x_i is an internal vertex of a tree T in \mathcal{J} then $\deg_T(x_i) \geq 2m - 2 + k - (m - 2) = m + k$. This implies that in any minimum graphoidal tree cover exactly one vertex of X should be internal in a tree. But there are m vertices and $|\mathcal{J}| \leq m - 1$. This leads to a contradiction. Hence $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \geq m$. Clearly, $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) \leq m$ and so

$$\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) = m. \quad \square$$

The following examples illustrate $\gamma_T(K_{m,n}) = \lceil \frac{m+n}{3} \rceil$.

Example 3.5 (i) Consider $K_{4,5}$. Clearly $k = 0$ and $r = 1$.

Fig.5

(ii) Consider $K_{8,9}$. Clearly $r = 2$ and $k = 1$.

Fig.6

(iii) Consider $K_{12,13}$. Clearly $r = 3$ and $k = 2$.

Fig.7

§4. Product of paths and cycles

- Theorem 4.1** (a) $\gamma_T(P_m \times P_n) = 2$ for integers $m, n \geq 2$;
 (b) $\gamma_T(P_n \times C_m) = 2$ for integers $m \geq 3, n \geq 2$;
 (c) $\gamma_T(C_m \times C_n) = 3$ for integers $m, n \geq 3$.

Proof The fact that $P_m \times C_{2r}$ and $P_m \times C_{2r+1}$ can be decomposed into graphoidal tree covers of order 2 clearly follows from Fig.11 and Fig.12. Hence (b) follows. It is easily seen that deleting the edges $(W_{i1}, W_{in}), i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ (from Fig.8, Fig.9 and Fig.10) produces a graphoidal tree cover for $P_m \times P_n$ and so (a) follows. Since $C_m \times C_n$ is 4-regular, $\gamma_T(C_m \times C_n) > 2$. Now consider the minimum graphoidal tree cover $\{T_1, T_2\}$ of $P_{m-1} \times C_n$.

Fig.8

Fig.9

$P_6 \times P_9$

Fig.10

Here in Fig.11 and Fig.12 thick lines form the tree T_1 and dotted lines form the tree T_2 .

Case (i) n is even.

To the tree T_2 , add vertices $w_{m,2}$ and $w_{m,4}$. Then add a vertex $w_{m,3}$ adjacent to $w_{1,3}$, $w_{m-1,3}$, $w_{m,2}$ and $w_{m,4}$. The only additional internal vertex this creates is $w_{m,3}$.

Fig.11

Now take a third tree as $T_3 = \{(w_{m,i-1}, w_{m,i}) : 2 \leq i \leq n; i \neq 3, 4\} \cup \{(w_{m,1}, w_{m,n})\} \cup \{(w_{m,i}, w_{1,i}), (w_{m,i}, w_{m-1,i}) : 1 \leq i \leq n; i \neq 3\}$.

Case (ii) n is odd.

To the tree T_2 , add vertices $w_{m,1}$ and $w_{m,3}$. Then add a vertex $w_{m,2}$ adjacent to $w_{1,2}$, $w_{m-1,2}$, $w_{m,1}$, $w_{m,3}$. The only additional internal vertex this creates is $w_{m,2}$.

Fig.12

Now take a third tree as $T_3 = \{(w_{m,i-1}, w_{m,i}) : 4 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{(w_{m,1}, w_{m,n})\} \cup \{(w_{m,i}, w_{1,i}), (w_{m,i}, w_{m-1,i}) : 1 \leq i \leq n; i \neq 2\}$. Now $\{T_1, T_2, T_3\}$ is a graphoidal tree cover for $C_m \times C_n$ and so $\gamma_T(C_m \times C_n) = 3$.

Observation 4.2 It is observed that $\tau(G) \leq \gamma_T(G)$. From Theorems 2.1 and 3.1, it follows that (i) $\tau(K_n) = \gamma_T(K_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$. It is also observed that $\tau(G) = \gamma_T(G)$ for all graphs with maximum degree ≤ 3 . From Theorems 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4, it follows that

Theorem 4.3 If G is a 2-connected cubic graph with p vertices, $p \geq 8$, then $\gamma_T(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{p}{4} \rfloor$.

Theorem 4.4 If G is a 3-connected cubic graph with p vertices, $p \geq 12$, then $\gamma_T(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{p}{6} \rfloor$.

Theorem 4.5 If G is a cyclically 4-edge connected cubic graph with p vertices, $8 \leq p \leq 16$ then $\gamma_T(G) = 2$.

§5. Relationship between $\tau'(G)$ and $\gamma_T(G)$

In [5] Foregger, M F and Foregger, T.H defined $\tau'(G)$ as the minimum number of subsets into which $V(G)$ can be partitioned so that each subset induces a tree. In this section we try to find some relationship between $\tau'(G)$ and $\gamma_T(G)$.

Theorem 5.1 *Let G be a graph with vertices $p \geq 4$ and let $\mathcal{J} = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$ be a minimum graphoidal tree cover of G with $|E(T_j)| = 1$ for some j and $|E(T_i)| > 1$ for all $i \neq j$. Then we can always find a minimum graphoidal tree cover $\mathcal{J}' = \{T'_1, T'_2, \dots, T'_n\}$ with $|E(T'_i)| > 1$ for all i .*

Proof Let $T_j = \{(xy)\}$. Consider cases following.

Case (i) Suppose at least one of the vertices x and y , say x , is internal in a tree of \mathcal{J} . First assume that x is internal in a tree T_i of \mathcal{J} . If $y \notin V(T_i)$ then replacing T_i by $T_i \cup T_j$ and removing T_j from \mathcal{J} , we get a graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}' with $|\mathcal{J}'| < |\mathcal{J}|$. Hence $y \in V(T_i)$. Let (w, x, z, \dots, y) be a path in T_i . Let C_1 and C_2 be the two components of $T_i - (xz)$ containing x and y respectively. Replace T_i and T_j by $C_2 \cup (xz)$ and $C_1 \cup T_j$ respectively so that both of them have at least two edges. Now \mathcal{J} is still a minimum graphoidal tree cover and $|E(T)| > 1$ for every $T \in \mathcal{J}$.

Case (ii) Suppose both x and y are external vertices in \mathcal{J} . If $x \in V(T_i)$ and $y \notin V(T_i)$ then as in Case (i), we get a graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}' with $|\mathcal{J}'| < |\mathcal{J}|$. Hence either $x, y \in V(T)$ or $x, y \notin V(T)$ for every T in \mathcal{J} . Let $x, y \in V(T_r)$, $T_r \in \mathcal{J}$. Suppose $|E(T_r)| > 2$. Let $e = (xz)$ be an edge in T_r . Replace T_r and T_j by $T_r - e$ and $T_j \cup e$ respectively and the result is true in this case. So let us assume that $|E(T_i)| = 2$ for some $T_i \in \mathcal{J}$ and $x, y \in V(T_i)$. Suppose $T_i = (xzy) \in \mathcal{J}$. Then $\deg(z) \geq 3$ in G . For, suppose $\deg(z) = 2$ in G . Since G is connected and $p \geq 4$, we must have at least one of the vertices x, y is of degree ≥ 3 . Since x or y alone can not be a member of a tree in \mathcal{J} and $x, y \in V(T_i), V(T_j)$ we have $\deg(x) \geq 3$ and $\deg(y) \geq 3$.

Let x and y be external vertices in a tree T_r of \mathcal{J} ($r \neq i, j$). Replace T_r and T_j by $T_r \cup (xz)$ and $T_j \cup (zy)$ respectively. Now $\{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_{i-1}, T_{i+1}, \dots, T_n\}$ is clearly a graphoidal tree cover for G . This is a contradiction to the minimality of \mathcal{J} . Hence $\deg(z) \geq 3$ in G . Now, z must be external in some tree T_r of \mathcal{J} . Clearly $x, y \in V(T_r)$. Suppose $x, y \notin V(T_r)$. Replace T_r and T_j by $T_r \cup \{(xz)\}$ and $T_j \cup \{(zy)\}$ respectively in \mathcal{J} . Now $\{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_{i-1}, T_{i+1}, \dots, T_n\}$ is clearly a graphoidal tree cover for G . This is a contradiction to the minimality of \mathcal{J} . It shows that $x, y \in V(T_r)$. Since x, y and z are external vertices in T_r we have $|E(T_r)| \geq 3$. Let e be an edge in T_r containing z . Replace T_i and T_j by $\{T_i - (xz)\} \cup \{e\}$ and $T_j \cup \{(xz)\}$ respectively. Now \mathcal{J} is a minimum graphoidal tree cover and $|E(T)| > 1$ for every $T \in \mathcal{J}$. \square

Proposition 5.2 *If $p \geq 4$, then there exists a minimum graphoidal tree cover of a connected graph G , in which every tree has more than one edge.*

Proof Let \mathcal{J} be a minimum graphoidal tree cover of G and let $\mathcal{J} = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$. Let us assume that $T_i = \{e_i\}$, $1 \leq i \leq k$ and $|E(T_j)| > 1$ for $k+1 \leq j \leq n$. Let $G' = G - \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\}$. Clearly $\mathcal{J}' = \mathcal{J} - \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k\}$ is a graphoidal tree cover for G' . Suppose G' is a disconnected graph. Then the number of components $\omega(G')$ is greater than one. If $\omega(G' \cup e_i) = \omega(G')$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ then G is disconnected. Hence we can choose $e_i = (x_i, y_i)$ for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ such that $\omega(G' \cup e_i) < \omega(G')$. Let G'_1, G''_1 be the components of G' such that $G'_1 \cup G''_1 \cup e_i$ is connected. Without loss of generality assume that $x_i \in G'_1$, $y_i \in G''_1$. If at all x_i is internal in a tree of \mathcal{J} , let it be in a tree T (of \mathcal{J}) in G'_1 . Clearly $\mathcal{J}_1 = (\mathcal{J} - \{T, T_i\}) \cup \{T \cup T_i\}$ is a graphoidal tree cover of G

and $\mathcal{J}_1 < |\mathcal{J}|$. This is a contradiction. Hence G' is connected. Take $G_1 = G' \cup \{e_1\}$. Clearly $\mathcal{J}_1 = \mathcal{J}' \cup \{T_1\}$ is a minimum graphoidal tree cover for G_1 and $|\mathcal{J}_1| = n - k + 1$. For, suppose $\gamma_T(G_1) < n - k + 1$ and let \mathcal{J}'' be a minimum graphoidal tree cover for G_1 . Then $|\mathcal{J}''| < n - k + 1$. Since $G = G_1 \cup \{e_2, \dots, e_k\}$, $\mathcal{J}''' = \mathcal{J}'' \cup \{T_2, \dots, T_k\}$ is a graphoidal tree cover for G and $|\mathcal{J}'''| = |\mathcal{J}''| + k - 1 < n - k + 1 + k - 1 = n$. This is a contradiction to the minimality of \mathcal{J} . Hence $\gamma_T(G_1) = n - k + 1$. By Theorem 5.1, there exists a minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}'_1 of G_1 in which every tree has more than one edge and $|\mathcal{J}'_1| = |\mathcal{J}_1| = n - k + 1$. Let $G_2 = G_1 \cup \{e_2\}$. Proceeding as above, we find a minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}_2 of G_2 in which every tree has more than one edge. Finally, we get $G = G_n = G_{n-1} \cup \{e_n\}$ and by a similar argument as above, we find a minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J}_n of $G = G_n$ in which $|E(T)| > 1$ for every $T \in \mathcal{J}_n$. \square

Lemma 5.3 *Let $p(G) \geq 4$. Let \mathcal{J} be a graphoidal tree cover of G such that $|E(T)| > 1$ for every tree $T \in \mathcal{J}$. Let $i(T)$ be the set of internal vertices of T . Then $\langle i(T) \rangle$ -the subgraph induced by $i(T)$ is a subgraph of T and it is a tree for every $T \in \mathcal{J}$.*

Proof If $|i(T)| = 1$ then clearly the result is true. Let $|i(T)| > 1$. Let $x, y \in i(T)$ and $xy \in E(G)$. Suppose $xy \notin E(T)$. Then there exists T' of \mathcal{J} such that $T' = \{(xy)\}$ by the definition of graphoidal tree cover. By our assumption this is not possible. Hence $\langle i(T) \rangle$ is a subgraph of T and it is a tree. Moreover, it is got by removing all the pendant vertices of T . \square

Theorem 5.4 *If G is a (p, q) graph with $p \geq 4$, then $\tau'(G) \leq \gamma_T(G)$.*

Proof By Proposition 5.2, we have known that result (1) following:

there exists a minimum graphoidal tree cover \mathcal{J} such that $|E(T)| > 1$ for all $T \in \mathcal{J}$ and $|\mathcal{J}| = n$.

Let $\mathcal{J} = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$.

Case (i) If every vertex is an internal vertex of a tree of \mathcal{J} , then $V(G) = i(T_1) \cup \dots \cup i(T_n)$ is clearly a vertex partition of G . By Lemma 5.3, $\langle i(T_j) \rangle$ is a subgraph of T_j and is a tree for $1 \leq j \leq n$. Hence $\tau'(G) \leq n \leq \gamma_T(G)$.

Case (ii) Let x be one of the vertices which is not internal in any tree of \mathcal{J} . Let $x \in V(T_k)$ and $v \in i(T_k)$ such that $xv \in E(T_k)$. Since x is not internal in any tree of \mathcal{J} and v is not internal in any tree except T_k , we have $\langle i(T_k) \cup \{x\} \rangle$ is a tree. For, if $xu \in E(G)$ and $xu \notin E(T_k)$ where $u \neq v$ in $i(T_k)$, then by the definition of graphoidal tree cover there exists T' of \mathcal{J} such that $T' = \{(xu)\}$. This is a contradiction to claim in (1).

Let x, y be non-internal vertices in any tree of \mathcal{J} . Let $x, y \in V(T_k)$. If $xy \in E(G)$ then there exists T' of \mathcal{J} such that $T' = \{(xy)\}$. This is a contradiction to the claim (1) also. Clearly, in this case $\langle i(T_k) \cup \{x, y\} \rangle$ is a tree. In this way we adjoin every such vertex to an $i(T_k)$. We make sure that each such vertex is adjoined to only one $i(T_k)$. These induced subgraphs give rise to a partition of $V(G)$ and these induced subgraphs form $n = \gamma_T(G)$ trees. Hence $\tau'(G) \leq n = \gamma_T(G)$. From Theorems 3.1 and 4.1 it follows that $\gamma_T(G) = \tau'(G)$ for the following graphs $K_n, P_m \times P_n$ and $P_n \times C_m$. \square

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